

A Novel Extension of Rayleigh Distribution: Characterization, Estimation, Simulations and Applications

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce a novel probability distribution called the Lambert-Rayleigh (LR) distribution to address limitations observed in existing distributions, particularly the Rayleigh Distribution. Standard distributions often struggle to accurately model data that exhibits skewness and heavy tails. The LRD offers a flexible three-parameter framework that enhances its ability to model asymmetric and heavy-tailed data. This contrasts with the Rayleigh Distribution, which is constrained by a fixed shape parameter and a single-mode structure, limiting its applicability in diverse datasets. We applied the Lambert-Rayleigh Distribution (LRD) in two distinct case studies to demonstrate its efficacy. First, we analyzed a dataset from Shasta Reservoir, focusing on yearly water capacity within a specific range. Second, we examined Kevlar 373/epoxy materials in the context of fatigue fracture life. In both cases, the LRD exhibited superior modeling performance compared to other distributions commonly used in these domains. The Lambert-Rayleigh Distribution thus represents a significant advancement in probability modeling, offering enhanced flexibility and accuracy in capturing the complex statistical characteristics often found in real-world data.

Keywords— Lambert W function, Lambert-G family, Rayleigh distribution, Goodness of fit, Estimation.

1 Introduction

Statistical distributions play a crucial role in facilitating deeper understanding and effective modeling of diverse observations within statistical frameworks. They enable researchers to comprehend data more comprehensively and draw conclusions based on the model provided by the distribution. By estimating distribution parameters, statistical methods can analyze samples or large datasets, enhancing the reliability of statistical inferences and enabling more informed decisions and precise conclusions. This underscores the significance of statistical distributions in empowering researchers, engineers, medical practitioners, and decision-makers to confidently navigate the complexities and uncertainties of the world.

Statistical distributions are categorized into families based on similarities in parameters, mathematical properties, relationships, and practical applications in real-world data. Examples include the Pareto Distribution [4], Beta Exponential Distribution [31], Weibull Distribution [27], and Cauchy Distribution [21].

In pursuit of understanding a broader range of datasets and their patterns, statisticians often create new distributions by augmenting parameters of existing ones. This process yields modified distributions that capture complexities overlooked by simpler models. Modifying a distribution enhances its flexibility, making it easier to interpret and explain statistical analysis results, thus enabling more accurate conclusions. Examples of such modified distributions include the Chris-Jerry Distribution and Its Applications [41], Weibull Distribution with

Estimable Shift Parameter [39], Exponentiated Weibull-Weibull Distribution [11], Weibull Rayleigh Distribution [29], and a New Modification of Shanker Distribution [14]. Developing new distributions through parameter augmentation provides valuable insights and tools for addressing diverse challenges encountered in analysis and modeling.

The Lambert-G family of distributions exemplifies this innovation in probability [2]. Derived from the Lambert W-Function, also known as the Product Logarithm [46], Lambert-G distributions leverage this function to solve complex scenarios involving exponential and logarithmic terms.

Lambert-G distributions are renowned for their versatility and robustness in handling data with skewness, heavy tails, and other complex behaviors. They are based on the Lambert W function, which solves equations of the form $W(x)e^{W(x)} = x$.

The Lambert W function finds applications in various fields such as engineering, combinatorics, probability distributions, statistical modeling, and thermodynamics [7]. Introduced by Johann Heinrich Lambert in the 18th century, its extensive study and popularity owe much to the seminal work of Robert M. Corless and colleagues, particularly their 1996 paper "On the Lambert W Function" [8], which highlighted its broad applications across disciplines.

The Lambert G family of distributions utilizes the Lambert W function to transform a baseline random variable \mathbf{X} from a known distribution \mathbf{F} . See [25]. We can express this transformation as

$$Y = \mu + \sigma W \left(\frac{X - \mu}{\sigma} \right),$$

where,

- X is a random variable from the baseline distribution F .
- μ and σ are location and scale parameters, respectively.
- W is the Lambert W function applied to the standardized variable $\frac{X-u}{\sigma}$.

The Lambert W function enhances the LG family of distributions by enabling the transformation of baseline distributions to introduce skewness and heavy tails, thus providing greater flexibility and accuracy in modeling complex real-world data thereby enhancing their versatility and precision in modeling complex and real-world data behaviors that deviate from traditional symmetric and light-tailed distributions. This brought about better results when applied to various distributions such as Lambert-Lomax distribution, Lambert F-Distribution See [23], Lambert-Exponential distribution, and many others. .

The Lambert-G family of distribution has the cumulative distribution function (cdf) and probability density function (pdf) as:

$$F(x; \alpha, \theta, \xi) = 1 - \exp \left(- \left\{ -\ln [\bar{G}(x, \xi)] \right\}^\theta \exp \left\{ -\alpha \ln [\bar{G}] (x; \xi) \right\} \right), \quad (1)$$

and

$$f(x; \theta, \alpha, \xi) = \frac{\left\{ \alpha - \alpha \ln [\bar{G}(x; \xi)] \right\} \ln(x; \xi)}{\left\{ -\ln [\bar{G}(x; \xi)] \right\}^{1-\theta}} \exp \left\{ -\alpha \ln [\bar{G}(x; \xi)] \right\} \bar{F}(x; \theta, \alpha, \xi), \quad (2)$$

respectively.

Where β is the vector of parameters of the baseline distribution While α and θ are the additional shape parameters.

The Rayleigh Distribution was proposed in 1880 by an English Mathematician, John William Strutt, 3rd Baron Rayleigh, [12]. The application of Rayleigh Distribution ranges from clinical research and studies to real-life testing of experiments and life-data analysis. Its cumulative distribution function (cdf) and probability density function (pdf) are versatile in fields such as Wind Speed Modeling [28], Quality Control [20], Fluid Dynamic Simulation [19], Image Analysis [24], Measurement Of Wave Heights [26], etc, The Rayleigh Distribution has its pdf as:

$$G(x; \delta) = 1 - e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\delta^2}}; x > 0, \quad \delta > 0, \quad (3)$$

and cdf as:

$$g(x; \delta) = \frac{x}{\delta^2} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\delta^2}}, \quad (4)$$

respectively, where δ is the scale parameter of the distribution.

In application to the various fields mentioned above, The RD is often used due to its relevance in modeling and analyzing phenomena that involve the magnitude of two-dimensional vectors with normally distributed orthogonal components. The scaling factors in these fields are crucial as they normalize or adapt to the Rayleigh distribution to fit specific datasets and patterns. Acknowledging these scaling factors allows for more accurate modeling and interpretation of data across different disciplines. While valuable in specific contexts such as modeling wind speeds and signal processing, the Rayleigh distribution has notable limitations that restrict its broader applicability. One key limitation is its inherent assumption of a single mode, making it unsuitable for data that exhibit multiple peaks or modes. Additionally, it lacks the flexibility to model data with significant skewness or heavy tails which limits its use to datasets where this constraint holds. As a result, the Rayleigh distribution cannot adequately model data with significant deviations from its assumed shape, necessitating the use of more flexible distributions [9]. There are many flexible distributions in the literature, see [35, 10, 38, 32, 13, 18, 17, 6, 33, 34, 36, 16, 40, 43, 15, 37, 44, 5, 45, 42, 30, 1] for more.

The main purpose of inducing the Lambert-G family into the Rayleigh distribution is to introduce skewness and heavy tails, enhancing the flexibility and accuracy of the Rayleigh distribution in modeling real-world data. The transformation, derived by applying the Lambert W function to the baseline Rayleigh variable, results in a new variable that can better capture asymmetry and extreme values, which are often present in empirical data. This makes the new Lambert-Rayleigh Distribution more adaptable to various fields such as engineering, environmental science, finance, and medical imaging, where data often deviate from the typical symmetric and light-tailed nature of the traditional Rayleigh distribution. By accommodating these deviations, the Lambert-G family transformation improves the fit and modeling capability of the Rayleigh distribution.

2 The Lambert-Rayleigh (LR) Distribution

The Lambert-Rayleigh Distribution coined from 1, 2, 3, and 4 having cdf

$$F(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta) = 1 - \exp\left(\frac{-x^{2\theta}}{2\theta\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}}\right); \quad x \geq 0, \quad \theta, \alpha, \delta > 0. \quad (5)$$

where δ is the scale parameter. and have its pdf as

$$f(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta) = \frac{x^{2\theta-1}}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} - \frac{x^{2\theta}}{2\theta\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}}\right). \quad (6)$$

The survival function and the hazard rate function are:

$$s(x) = \exp\left(\frac{-x^{2\theta}}{2\theta\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}}\right), \quad (7)$$

and

$$h(x) = \frac{x^{2\theta-1}}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}\right), \quad (8)$$

respectively.

Figure 1 is the two-dimensional plot of the pdf of the proposed LR distribution having different unique shapes that offers it to more applications than the parent Rayleigh distribution.

Figure 1: pdf plots of LR (θ, α, δ)

(a) hrf of LR (θ, α, δ)

(b) hrf of LR (θ, α, δ)

(c) hrf of LR (θ, α, δ)

(d) hrf of LR (θ, α, δ)

Figure 2: hazard rate function

Figure 2 is the different shapes of the hazard function of the LR distribution.

Figure 3: mean of LR (θ, α, δ)

Figure 4: variance of LR (θ, α, δ)

The mean and variance are plotted in figures 3 and 4 respectively.

3 Characterization

This section focuses on studying some vital mathematical components of the new model which includes the crude moment and its measures, distribution of the order statistics and the mean residual life function.

3.1 Moment

The obtained r th crude moment of LR Distribution is:

$$\mu'_r = \int_0^\infty x^r f(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta) dx = \int_0^\infty x^r \frac{x^{2\theta-1}}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} \right) \exp\left(\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} - \frac{x^{2\theta}}{2\theta\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) dx \tag{9}$$

So that

$$\mu'_r = \frac{1}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left\{ \phi \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + r + 2\}\right) + \Psi \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + r + 2\}\right) \right\}, \tag{10}$$

where

$$\phi = -\frac{\theta\delta^2}{j\alpha} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^\infty \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+r-2\}} \frac{\alpha^{i-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j+1}},$$

$$\Psi = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^\infty \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \frac{\alpha^{i-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j-i}} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+r\}},$$

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + r\} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = \frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + r + 2\}.$$

The mean is the first crude moment obtained by substituting 1 for r in equation 10

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_1 = & \frac{1}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left\{ \frac{-\theta\delta^2}{j\alpha} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)-1\}} \frac{\alpha^{i-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j+1}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + 1\}\right) \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{-1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+1\}} \frac{\alpha^{-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j-1}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + 3\}\right) \right] \right\} \tag{11} \end{aligned}$$

The second, third and fourth crude moments are given as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_2 = & \frac{1}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left\{ \frac{-\theta\delta^2}{j\alpha} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)\}} \frac{\alpha^{i-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + 2\}\right) \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{-1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+2\}} \frac{\alpha^{-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j-1}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + 4\}\right) \right] \right\}, \tag{12} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_3 = & \frac{1}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left\{ \frac{-\theta\delta^2}{j\alpha} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+1\}} \frac{\alpha^{i-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + 3\}\right) \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{-1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(-\frac{2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+3\}} \frac{\alpha^{-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j-1}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} \{2\theta(j+1) + 2(i-j) + 5\}\right) \right] \right\}, \tag{13} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mu'_4 = \frac{1}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left\{ \frac{-\theta\delta^2}{j\alpha} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(\frac{-2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+2\}} \frac{\alpha^{i-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+4\}\right) \right. \\ \left. + \left[\frac{-1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} \frac{(-1)^j}{i!} \left(\frac{-2\delta^2}{j\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+4\}} \frac{\alpha^{-j}}{2^{j(\theta-1)+i}\delta^{2(\theta-1)j-1}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\{2\theta(j+1)+2(i-j)+6\}\right) \right] \right\}, \quad (14)$$

respectively.

Figure 5: skewness of LR (θ, α, δ)

Figure 6: kurtosis of LR (θ, α, δ)

The skewness and the kurtosis are plotted in figures 5 and 6 respectively.

3.2 Distribution of Order Statistics

The PDF of the p -th order statistic $X_{(p)}$ from a random sample x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with PDF $f(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta)$ and CDF $F(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta)$, where $1 \leq p \leq n$, is given by:

$$f_{X_{(p)}}(x; n, \theta, \alpha, \delta) = \binom{n-1}{p-1} F(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta)^{p-1} [1 - F(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta)]^{n-p} f(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta).$$

Here,

- $f_{X_{(p)}}(x; n, \theta, \alpha, \delta)$ is the PDF of the p -th order statistic $X_{(p)}$.
- $\binom{n-1}{p-1}$ is the binomial coefficient.
- $F(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta)$ is the CDF of the underlying distribution.
- $f(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta)$ is the PDF of the underlying distribution.

For the proposed LR distribution, the distribution of the p -th order statistic is expressed as;

$$f_{p:n}(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta) = \binom{n}{p} \frac{x^{2\theta-1}}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} \right) \exp\left(\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} - \frac{x^{2\theta}}{2\theta\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) \\ \times \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{x^{2\theta}}{2\theta\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) \right]^{p-1} \left[\exp\left(-\frac{x^{2\theta}}{2\theta\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) \right]^{n-p} \quad (15)$$

The distribution of the largest order statistics is obtained for $p = n$, which is

$$f_{n:n}(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta) = \frac{x^{2\theta-1}}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} - \frac{x^{2\theta}}{2^{\theta}\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-\frac{x^{2\theta}}{2^{\theta}\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) \right]^{n-1} \quad (16)$$

The distribution of the smallest order statistics is obtained for $p = 1$, which is

$$f_{1:n}(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta) = \frac{nx^{2\theta-1}}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta}} \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2} - \frac{x^{2\theta}}{2^{\theta}\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) \left[\exp \left(-\frac{x^{2\theta}}{2^{\theta}\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) \right]^{n-1} \quad (17)$$

3.3 Mean Residual Life Function

In life testing experiments, the expected additional lifetime given that a component has survived until time t is a function of t , called the mean residual life. More specifically, if the random variable X represents the life of a component, then the mean residual life is given by $m(x) = E(X - x | X > x)$. For the proposed LR distribution, it is given as

$$m_{rl}(x) = E[X - x | X > x] = \frac{1}{1 - F(x)} \int_x^\infty [1 - F(t)] dt = \frac{2^{\theta+1}\sigma^{2(\theta+1)}}{[4\theta\sigma x^{2\theta-1} + \alpha x^{2\theta+1}]} e^{-\frac{\alpha t^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (18)$$

4 Estimation of the Parameters

The maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) is essential for inference, hypothesis testing, and construction of confidence intervals, making it a fundamental tool in both theoretical and applied statistics. This involves selecting the parametric form of the LR Distribution and its associated likelihood function and using it to find the parameter values that make the observed data most probable, typically by maximizing the product of the probability density function evaluated at each observed data point. Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be n observations from a random sample which assumes the LR distribution with parameters $\xi = (\theta, \delta, \alpha)$, then the likelihood function for the parameters ξ is expressed as follows;

$$L(x; \theta, \alpha, \delta) = \frac{1}{(2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta})^n} e^{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2} - \frac{x_i^{2\theta}}{2^{\theta}\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2}} \right)} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{2\theta-1} \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2} \right) \quad (19)$$

Take the natural logarithm of both sides and set $\ln L = \phi$

$$\phi = -n(\theta - 1) \ln 2 - 2\theta n \ln \delta + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2} - \frac{x_i^{2\theta}}{2^{\theta}\delta^{2\theta}} e^{\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \left[(2\theta - 1) \ln x_i + \ln \left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2} \right) \right] \quad (20)$$

Taking the first partial derivatives of ϕ with respect to θ, α , and δ , we realize the following non-linear system of equations;

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} = -n \ln 2 - 2 \ln \delta - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i^2}{2\delta^2} \right)^\theta \ln \left(\frac{x_i^2}{2\delta^2} \right) e^{\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2}} + \sum_{i=1}^n \left[2 \ln x_i + \frac{1}{\theta + \frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2}} \right] \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \delta} = \frac{-2\theta n}{\delta} + \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\theta x_i^{2\theta}}{2^{\theta-1}\delta^{2\theta+1}} e^{\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2}} - \frac{\alpha x_i^2}{\delta^3} + \frac{\alpha x_i^{2\theta+2}}{2^{\theta}\delta^{2\theta+3}} e^{\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2}} \right] - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha x_i^2}{\left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2} \right) \delta^3} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i^2}{2\delta^2} + \frac{x_i^2}{2\delta^2} e^{\frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2}} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\left(\theta + \frac{\alpha x_i^2}{2\delta^2} \right) 2\delta^2} \quad (23)$$

5 Applications of LR Distribution

An observation of the Shasta Reservoir located in California on the months of February focusing on the water capacity from 1991 to 2010. The Data gotten from [22] is as follows: 0.0833, 0.0833, 0.1167, 0.1167, 0.1167, 0.15, 0.1833, 0.2167, 0.2167, 0.25, 0.25, 0.25, 0.25, 0.2833, 0.3167, 0.35, 0.3833, 0.4167, 0.4167, 0.45, 0.4833, 0.4833, 0.7167, 0.7167, 0.75, 0.75, 0.85, 0.9167

Table 1: Measures of model performance and fitness

Distr.	LL	AIC	CAIC	BIC	HQIC	W	A	K-S	P-value
LR	3.81	-1.6124	-0.6124	2.3842	-0.3906	0.0682	0.4918	0.1220	0.7987
Gamma	4.11	-0.0455	0.4345	2.6189	0.7691	0.04451	0.3632	0.18153	0.3147
Weibull	3.78	-3.428	-2.948	-0.764	-2.613	0.06265	0.4648	0.14425	0.6048

Table 2: MLE estimates of the parameters of the fitted distributions

LR	Est.	Gamma	Est.	Weibull	Est.
θ	0.7865	α	1.7238	α	1.6673
α	0.0291	β	0.2787	β	0.4427
δ	0.3092				

Figure 7: Density, cdf, survival and TTT plots for strength of the water capacity

The second application is an incomplete dataset of Kevlar 373/epoxy material which focuses on the fatigue fracture life of the material when exposed to a constant pressure which brings about a 90% stress level thereby causing failure in the material. The data gotten from [3] is as follows: 0.0251, 0.0886, 0.0891, 0.2501, 0.3113, 0.3451, 0.4763, 0.5650, 0.5671, 0.6566, 0.6748, 0.6751, 0.6753, 0.7696, 0.8375, 0.8391, 0.8425, 0.8645, 0.8851, 0.9113, 0.9120, 0.9836, 1.0483, 1.0596, 1.0773, 1.1733, 1.2570, 1.2766, 1.2985, 1.3211, 1.3503, 1.3551, 1.4595, 1.4880, 1.5728, 1.5733, 1.7083, 1.7263, 1.7460, 1.7630, 1.7746

Table 3: Measures of model performance and fitness

Distr.	NLL	AIC	CAIC	BIC	HQIC	W	A	K-S	P-value
LR	25.93	57.8606	58.5092	63.0013	59.7325	0.0448	0.3081	0.0905	0.8604
Gamma	33.99	74.0671	74.0671	78.1784	75.9992	0.2071	1.3929	0.1751	0.1433
Weibull	30.65	65.3680	65.6838	68.7951	66.6159	0.1098	0.8126	0.1190	0.5664

Table 4: MLE estimates of the parameters of the fitted distributions

LR	Est.	Gamma	Est.	Weibull	Est.
θ	0.4996	α	1.5980	α	1.8769
α	3.1523	β	0.6520	β	1.0833
δ	1.7814				

Figure 8: Density, cdf, survival and TTT plots for strength of the Kevlar 373/epoxy material

We obtain the Maximum Likelihood Estimates (MLE) and their corresponding standard errors (in parentheses) for the model parameters. To compare the performance of different distribution models, we use criteria such as the negative log-likelihood function (NLL), Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistic, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Corrected Akaike Information Criterion (CAIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC) and p-value. A better distribution is indicated by smaller values of NLL, AIC, BIC, CAIC, HQIC, and K-S, along with a larger p-value. Additionally, we plot the histogram for each data set and the estimated probability density function (pdf) of the LR distribution. Figures 7 and 8 display the plots of the empirical cumulative distribution function (cdf) of the data sets and the estimated pdf of LR distribution, respectively.

6 Conclusion

The Lambert-Rayleigh Distribution demonstrates significant advancements in statistical modeling by offering enhanced flexibility to handle skewed and heavy-tailed data, outperforming traditional distributions like the Rayleigh distribution. Empirical applications, such as those involving data from the Shasra Reservoir and the fatigue fracture life of Kevlar 373/epoxy materials, reveal its superior fit and practical robustness. Effective parameter estimation methods, including Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) and the Method of Moments, ensure reliable and accurate inference. The Lambert-Rayleigh Distribution's versatility allows for detailed statistical analysis and modeling. With broad applicability across fields like engineering, environmental science, and material science, the Lambert-Rayleigh Distribution proves to be a valuable tool for addressing complex data distributions. Extending the Rayleigh distribution using the Lambert-G family, bringing about the Lambert-Rayleigh distribution, provides a powerful tool for modeling positively skewed data with versatile tail behaviors. This extension strengthens statistical modeling across diverse fields, particularly in managing non-negative data distributions with greater effectiveness.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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